

Conceptual framework on the implementation of workflows concerning appraisal, reappraisal, retention and preservation of digital objects: Retention (Re) Appraisal - Iteration Logic (RRAIL)

Authorship

Contribution	Name	ORCID ID	Affiliation
Author(s)	Hervé L'Hours	0000-0001-5137-3032	UK Data Archive
	Micky Lindlar	0000-0003-3709-5608	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology
	Jacques Flores-Dourojeanni	0000-0002-4123-6111	Utrecht University
Contributor(s)	Fen Zhang	0000-0001-7135-3960	KU Leuven
	Ulf Jakobsson	0000-0002-6724-8751	Swedish National Data Service
	Karl Presser	0000-0001-7644-4116	Premotec GmbH
	Olivier Rouchon	0000-0002-1816-5546	Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)
Reviewer(s)	Roxanne Wyns	0000-0002-7146-8239	KU Leuven
	Laura Molloy	0000-0002-5214-4466	CODATA
	Aoife Lawton	0000-0002-3040-8520	HSE Library

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Executive Summary

This document proposes an approach to the logical choices, including assessments and interventions, that must be iterated over time to ensure the correct digital objects are appropriately retained and maintained.

Effective digital object appraisal, retention and reappraisal are fundamental to maintaining a reliable research data infrastructure. The workflows presented here may be implemented by a variety of stakeholders such as repositories, archives, and other research data management service providers and are relevant to research data support staff such as data stewards and data curators.

Aligned with the EOSC Long-Term Data Retention (LTDR) Task Force's Terms of Reference; this paper on, Retention, (Re) Appraisal - Iteration Logic (RRAIL), draws on key work from the EOSC EDEN project

(e.g., Core Preservation Processes), the FIDELIS project (e.g., Transparent Trustworthy Attributes Matrix - TTRAM), and the CoreTrustSeal Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP). These inputs help define repository characteristics and the metadata required to communicate different levels of care.

Together, this document provides a coherent model for improving decision-making, transparency, and long-term management of digital objects across the EOSC ecosystem.

List of Abbreviations

LTDR-TF	Long-Term Data Retention Task Force
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (FIDELIS)
CPP	Core Preservation Processes (EDEN)
RRAIL	Retention, (Re) Appraisal - Iteration Logic
LoRCAP	Levels of Retention, Curation, and Preservation
A F	Activities or Functions (TTRAM)

Introduction

The appraisal and retention of digital objects is central to a functioning research digital object (data and metadata) infrastructure. Ideally, as time passes and circumstances change, digital objects are iteratively reappraised based on defined workflows and criteria. Models for such workflows must be inclusive of repositories offering distinct levels of care for digital objects.

The EOSC Long-Term Data Retention Task Force (LTDR-TF) proposes a series of logical iterative workflows that describe digital object assessment and intervention points through appraisal, retention and reappraisal. This retention and (re)appraisal iteration logic (RRAIL) presents a standardised

formulation of common repository practices to support the design and implementation of effective workflows¹.

This LTDR-TF output takes into account the work done thus far (Nov 2025) by the EOSC EDEN project² (particularly Core Preservation Processes - CPP³) and the FIDELIS project⁴ (particularly the Transparent Trustworthy Attributes Matrix - TTRAM⁵). The TTRAM includes the decision to examine repository 'types' in terms of characteristics related to their digital objects, their depositors, and their users. The RRAIL also uses the Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation⁶ (LoRCAP) and related work to define the metadata required to implement and communicate the levels⁷.

After providing an overview of the importance of digital object characteristics and repository capabilities, the three key components that underpin the RRAIL are described: TTRAM, LoRCAP, and CPP. They constitute the building blocks, definitions and guidelines that have been assimilated, reviewed and refined to construct a template workflow that a digital object will iteratively pass through.

This is followed by an explanation and visual depictions of the logical and iterative cycles that a digital object may undergo as it is appraised, reappraised and actively preserved throughout its retention.

Key AIF of the TTRAM lifecycle are then mapped onto RRAIL, in alignment with LoRCAP and the CPP. This report concludes with recommendations on integrated preservation planning. Appendix 1 provides a glossary while Appendix 2 details the metadata needed to support different levels of repository care.

Digital Object Characteristics and Repository Capabilities

Digital Object characteristics refer to file formats, metadata schemas and ontologies in addition to methods, content types and disciplinary coverage (Figure 1). These characteristics are often varied, multitudinous and complex. This paper focuses primarily on the points where repositories assess digital objects and intervene to change them or their level of retention and care. These assessments will strongly depend on which digital object characteristics are desirable (or undesirable) in a particular

¹ In line with the Long Term Data Retention Task Force Terms of Reference. https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/20241107_TF-Long-Term-Data-Retention-Terms-of-Reference.pdf

² Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188015>

³ EOSC EDEN. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452>

⁴ FIDELIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188078>

⁵ FIDELIS TTRAMatrix. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144159>

⁶ Curation and Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

⁷ CoreTrustSeal Levels of Curation and Preservation: Implied Repository and Object Metadata Characteristics. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12701324>

repository context. The specifics of those characteristics will influence the required repository skills and capabilities, but this will not be addressed in detail here. The EDEN project² will address some of these issues through a Reuse Fitness Framework.,

Whereas digital object characteristics are used in this report as criteria for appraisal and reappraisal, the capabilities of repositories are also relevant. The repository must have the skills and expertise, technical infrastructure, security, etc., to deliver the level of retention, curation or preservation offered for the digital object, in line with the specified policies and needs of the depositors and users. These capabilities are either available through internal capacity or via third parties. Maintaining these capabilities has costs which should be factored into overall repository service provision costs. The models and processes in this paper assume that budget, resource and capacity are planned in advance so that specific costs e.g. of storage or taking preservation actions, are not factors in every individual object assessment.

Although not the aim of this paper, it should also be noted that the characteristics of depositors and users are also capable of influencing appraisal and reappraisal.

Figure 1. Example Object Characteristics. This image shows some of the possible characteristics a digital object may have when submitted into a repository. The actual characteristics may differ depending on the type/scope/field of the repository. The classification of object characteristics into Semantic, Technical and Quality still requires further development.

Component 1: TTRAM

The FIDELIS Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix⁵ (TTRAM) supports the FIDELIS goal of better understanding and supporting a wide range of repositories (Figure 2). The TTRAM considers what repository information should be made transparent from thirty activities or functions (A/F). It also considers how this information is influenced by different variables, including LoRCAP (Figure 3). The focus of this paper is on the A/F related to the digital object management lifecycle.

Figure 2. TTRAM Digital Object Management Activities or Functions (A/F) workflow.

Component 2: Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)

The Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP) were developed by the CoreTrustSeal to better differentiate the levels of care offered by repositories and to identify which were in scope for CoreTrustSeal certification. They have been adopted by the EOSC-A Long Term Data Preservation⁸ and Retention⁹ Task Forces and used in the FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN Projects. The Levels are: Retention, Deposit Compliance, Initial Curation, and Active Preservation. It has been proposed by the CoreTrustSeal Board that repositories should declare information about their approach to retention, in terms of related metadata about both the object and repository¹⁰ (see Appendix 2 for more details).

Figure 3. LoRCAP Levels of Retention, Curation And Preservation. Repository levels of care will commonly build on these cumulatively, though it is conceptually possible to provide Active Preservation without Initial Curation.

Component 3: Core Preservation Processes (CPP)

The EOSC EDEN project identifies Core Preservation Processes³. The image below is a screenshot of the CPP visualiser¹⁰. Despite their focus on active preservation (in LoRCAP terms) repositories, many of the CPPs are also relevant to repositories offering other levels of care.

⁸ Long Term Data Preservation. <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

⁹ Long Term Data Retention Task Force. <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

¹⁰ Core Preservation Processes Visualizer. <https://cpp.fd-dev.csc.fi/>

Figure 4. Core Preservation Processes visualised. Each node depicts one of the 30 CPPs. The links between CPPs represent procedural relationships (e.g. “trigger”), dependencies (e.g. “required by”) and logical relationships (e.g. “not to be confused with”). Link to CPP visualizer: <https://cpp.fd-dev.csc.fi/>.

RRAIL Lifecycle of a Digital Object

If we take into consideration the aforementioned key components, we can now begin to visualise the lifecycle of a digital object as it enters into retention.

Appraisal

Deposit & Appraisal (TTRAM) involves Deposit Compliance (LoRCAP) and is the first of the Assessment and Intervention Points (see below). The selection of deposit compliance criteria may depend on whether the repository offers Initial Curation or Active Preservation. Deposit compliance assessments and outcomes may be relevant to later Reappraisal.

Figure 5. Submission and Appraisal. A repository may Accept or Reject the digital object being offered based on defined deposit compliance criteria. This assessment of digital objects' data and metadata may be machine-actionable or human-mediated. The option to 'resubmit' a digital object for deposit is implicit in 'reject' but excluded here to simplify the model.

Reappraisal

At the end of a period of retention and/or preservation a digital object will be reappraised. At that point retention may be continued, with or without an ongoing commitment to Active Preservation (LoRCAP). Otherwise, a digital object may be disposed of and deleted, potentially after being transferred to another repository for ongoing retention. Reappraisal could also be triggered early by other factors e.g. the planned closure of a repository.

At the point of reappraisal there are a limited number of outcomes.

- Retain without change (for a new, defined retention period);
- Retain with change to the digital object;
- Disposal, by:
 - Deleting from repository;
 - Custody transfer to another repository.

It is important to note that changes made to the digital object so that it meets the reappraisal criteria, once the reappraisal has been triggered (Figure 6), do not constitute Active Preservation.

Figure 6. Logical and iterative options from initial appraisal to deletion. Upon appraisal a digital object may be accepted into retention. After the retention period ends a digital object will undergo reappraisal (reappraisal may occur earlier due to external factors). Reappraisal is an assessment point wherein the digital object characteristics are compared to a set of reappraisal criteria to determine whether a digital object will continue to be retained with or without changes or be disposed of.

A repository that engages in Active Preservation (LoRCAP) also has the three outcomes of Change, No Change and Disposal, but also enables a digital object to change its status from 'active preservation' into 'retention-only' and vice versa (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Logical and iterative options from initial appraisal to deletion for active preservation repositories. When a repository offers active preservation a digital object will either be retained with or without an active preservation status. Upon reappraisal a digital object may or may not maintain its active preservation status based upon the reappraisal assessment. As shown in figure 6, the ability to maintain retention, or retention with active preservation may be done with or without changes to the digital object. Disposal remains a possible outcome of reappraisal.

Reappraisal Triggers and Criteria

Once reappraisal is triggered, the outcomes of the assessment (Figures 6 and 7) are determined based on how the digital object characteristics meet the reappraisal criteria (Figure 8). Reappraisal will be triggered by, inter alia, the end of a defined retention period. Both reappraisal and preservation involve using criteria to decide whether actions need to be taken on digital objects. The criteria may be related to digital object characteristics, internal policies, or external factors (e.g. technological deprecation or changes to user needs). Retention-only services will only assess and take action at the point of reappraisal. In contrast, Active Preservation repositories take ongoing actions when a need is identified by monitoring changes to technology and community factors. Future work on integrated preservation planning (below) will further explore the interaction of retention and preservation.

The digital object characteristics used for reappraisal criteria are identified through:

- **Compliance, adoption and adherence** to legislation, policies, rights and ethical standards;
- A **'Community Watch'**¹³ that engages with the designated community of users to identify relevant research methods, tools, formats, ontologies etc;
- A **'Technology Watch'**¹¹ that engages with parameters including storage and integrity, format support/redundancy, emulation methods etc.

Figure 8. Reappraisal Triggers and Criteria. Reappraisal occurs either at the end of an agreed retention period, or as a result of a trigger (e.g. closure of the repository) before that time is reached. There is a limited number of Reappraisal outcomes. It is conceptually possible that a digital object will be automatically deleted at the reappraisal point with no further assessment (e.g. for legal reasons based on a records retention schedule). The

¹¹ The systematic and iterative monitoring of technological advances and deprecations in the field preservation.

outcome of the reappraisal assessment is based on how the characteristics of the digital object meet the reappraisal criteria.

Other reappraisal topics include changes to:

- Repository mission and scope;
- Technology (e.g., software to support a format that becomes unavailable);
- User needs are monitored through “Technology Watch”¹¹ e.g., adoption of new technologies, formats, research methods.

In addition to digital characteristics, changes to the external factors above could mean a digital object is no longer retained. In this case, the object will either be deleted or custody could be transferred to another repository with different appraisal criteria.

Assessment and Intervention Points

This section further investigates the LoRCAP, TTRAM and RRAIL as assessment and intervention points in the digital object lifecycle. The RRAIL is first mapped onto the LoRCAP (Figure 9) to help us visualize the assessment points and how they relate to each level of care. In Figure 10 the LoRCAP is then mapped onto the TTRAM to see how each level relates to a specific TTRAM AIF.

The subsections further below then expand on the mappings created between the LoRCAP and the TTRAM AIF in Figure 10. These are Retention^{LoRCAP} and Deposit & Appraisal^{AIF} (adheres to deposit not to Appraisal); Deposit Compliance^{LoRCAP} and Deposit & Appraisal^{AIF}; Initial Curation^{LoRCAP} and Curation, Quality and Compliance^{AIF}.

Figure 9. LoRCAP Digital Object workflow. The diagram above shows the different operating workflows as the level of care for a digital object increases through basic retention, deposit compliance, initial curation and active preservation. In this diagram the reappraisal loops are simplified for clarity (e.g. no disposal shown); refer to Figures 6 and 7 for a detailed depiction of the reappraisal loops of both retention-only and active preservation repositories.

In the diagram above (Figure 9) we map simplified appraisal and reappraisal loops from RRAIL onto each LoRCAP level of care.

In the diagram below (Figure 10), the TTRAM lifecycle activities and functions (AIF) are aligned with the LoRCAP to identify the points at which a repository may assess and/or take action on a digital object.

Figure 10. Integration of TTRAM and LoRCAP. This diagram depicts the LoRCAP mapped to their respective A|F in the TTRAM.

The subsections below expand on the mappings between LoRCAP and TTRAM shown in Figure 10.

Retention (Minimum Viable Retention)

Retention:

The term ‘retention’ is used in a very narrow sense, and in line with the common usage¹² of ‘to keep’ e.g., a repository could offer unrestricted download of digital objects based on a resource discovery system with nothing more than a PID and a filename. Any more complex activities and functions are handled in higher levels of care (below).

Minimum retention information requires both an:

- Access method

¹² “the action of keeping something rather than losing it or stopping it” <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/retention>

- This could be unrestricted download of open data, in contrast to more complex scenarios where Access Rights and User Restrictions are required.
- Retention period
 - Any exceptions to the retention period that would trigger early reappraisal (e.g. closure of the repository).

Repositories that address more complicated reuse (e.g., secure data), access (e.g., non-Open digital objects), or offer initial curation or active preservation will have more complex processes, beginning with deposit compliance at the point of deposit and appraisal.

Deposit and Appraisal: Deposit Compliance

“Deposit Compliance

Data content and supporting metadata deposited are checked for compliance with defined criteria, e.g., data formats, metadata elements, and compliance with legal and ethical norms¹³ Digital objects that do not meet these criteria may be rejected, or moved forward to initial curation if provided by the repository.” (L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., & Recker, J., 2024, p. 9)

Minimum Viable Retention Information

We propose that the minimum Retention information necessary to support all Retention and Reappraisal should form a part of integrated preservation planning (below). This minimum retention information includes:

- **Retention period** start and end dates;
- **Triggers for reappraisal** (in addition to the end of the Retention Period), this could include the closure of the repository. Ideally, at the point of deposit the repository would begin to develop and communicate potential future reappraisal triggers;

¹³ The actions that follow these checks are determined by the repository. For example, a repository may choose to return (meta)data that does not meet the deposit criteria to the depositor, or to ingest the (meta)data and document non-compliance, or to undertake initial curation to ensure compliance.

- Reappraisal criteria.

In the text below, key terms from the source components are identified by superscript: Core Preservation Processes^{CPP}, Activities and Function^{AF} drawn from the TTRAM, and the Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation^{LORCAP}.

Other Information Outcomes from Deposit & Appraisal

At the end of the Deposit & Appraisal process the following information should be available:

- **Deposit criteria** (and assessment outcomes) is used to decide whether to accept or reject the object.
 - Any **exceptions** i.e., cases where the object does not meet deposit compliance criteria but is still accepted by the repository.
- Persistent identification (Discovery & Identification^{AF})
- Inclusion in a resource discovery catalogue (Discovery & Identification^{AF})
- Access conditions and methods (Rights^{AF}, Access^{AF})
- Bit-level measures to avoid unintended change (Storage & Integrity^{AF})

Repository Factors Influencing Deposit Criteria

The details of Deposit and Appraisal information, beyond that required for minimum viable retention, are driven by activities and functions later in the digital object lifecycle and the digital objects', depositors and potential users.

Deposit Compliance for Depositors

An institutional repository may only service depositors from one or more affiliated organisations.

Deposit Compliance for Users

The needs of the end users identified through Community Watch^{CPP} as a part of External Engagement^{AF} may guide which object characteristics are accepted or rejected e.g. disciplinary relevance.

Deposit Compliance for ReUse^{AF}

Some repositories may accept or reject more sensitive data that must be used within trustworthy research environments.

Deposit Compliance for Initial Curation^{LoRCAP}

A repository may accept a broader range of formats if it can convert these to desirable reuse formats during initial curation. A repository may accept less complete metadata if it can be created during Curation, Quality Compliance.

Deposit Compliance for Active Preservation^{LoRCAP}

A repository that offers active preservation may limit deposit format to those that are considered preservation friendly e.g. have a low risk of becoming redundant.

Deposit Compliance for Repository characteristics

The repository Mission and Scope^{AIF} may influence which depositor and object characteristics are accepted or rejected, and which users are part of the designated community. The repository must be capable of providing the activities and functions it offers for the digital objects it accepts.

Curation, Quality and Compliance: Initial Curation

“Initial Curation:

The digital objects are curated by the repository to meet defined criteria, which may exceed those defined for Deposit Compliance. This initial curation for access and use may include, e.g., the correction or enhancement of metadata and/or data content, or the creation of dissemination formats.” (L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., & Recker, J., 2024, p. 9)

Information Outcomes from Curation, Quality & Compliance

A repository may offer Initial Curation with or without an additional commitment to Active Preservation.

- **Curation Compliance Criteria** (and assessment outcomes) are used to guide initial curation actions.

Repository Factors Influencing Curation, Quality & Compliance

With the exception of "Depositor Compliance for Depositors" the factors relevant to Initial Curation reflect those in Deposit Compliance above plus:

Initial Curation for Active Preservation

A repository that offers active preservation may take steps during initial curation to mitigate long term preservation risks, this includes conversion to preservation-friendly file formats (i.e. .csv, .txt).

Assessment and Intervention: Active Preservation

"Active preservation:

The Repository takes long-term responsibility for ensuring that the data and metadata can be understood and rendered as required by the designated community for reuse.

The preservation actions can be aimed at logical-technical, semantic, or quality aspects of the (meta)data, for example, in response to the threat of technological obsolescence, to accommodate changing needs of the Designated Community, or in response to other considerations such as security or legal concerns.

Logical-technical measures include updating hard- and software environments, archival and dissemination formats of digital objects, and metadata. Semantic measures include updating the content of metadata elements and other semantic artefacts such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies if necessary. It may include responsibility for editing the structure and content of deposited data." (L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., & Recker, J., 2024, p. 9)

An Active Preservation repository undertaking "Community Watch" and "Technology Watch" may detect a risk to the accessibility and usability of a digital object at any time and choose to take remedial preservation actions to mitigate that risk.

Active Preservation responsibility must be designed in a way that interacts with Retention Guarantees. A reappraisal outcome of a preserved digital object might be to retain it for longer, but to stop actively preserving.

Integrated Preservation Planning

Integrated preservation planning refers to the measures taken by active preservation repositories to keep digital objects findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. These measures influence assessments which guide decisions or actions at the points of deposit, curation, and reappraisal. This paper advocates for an integrated approach to preservation planning, where all repository managers? share information about their levels of care, their object assessments, their outcomes and their actions. Consistent and transparent information at this level will clarify practices across repositories and objects, enabling the selection of the most appropriate repository for each digital object.

Though the EDEN Core Preservation Processes (CPP) focus on what the LoRCAP refers to as Active Preservation, the majority of the CPPs may be applied by repositories offering different levels of care.

With an integrated approach to preservation planning, these criteria can take into account the characteristics of the repository, the digital object, the depositors, and the users. Note that the CPPs provide an effective approach to storage and integrity measures.

This paper accepts that clear measures for avoiding and correcting unintended change (storage and integrity measures) should be in place for all levels of care. However, the focus here is on identifying the need for change and then taking actions to change digital objects and their data and/or metadata.

The Retention TF recommends that any repository should develop a public preservation plan that incorporates relevant 'core preservation processes' alongside reappraisal for retention. This includes repositories that do not offer Active Preservation^{LoRCAP}.

- Provenance and other information from deposit compliance^{LoRCAP}, initial curation^{LoRCAP} and active preservation^{LoRCAP} may provide input to future reappraisal decisions.
- Deposit compliance criteria may be influenced by the LoRCAP, particularly whether the repository can offer the required initial curation and active preservation.
- Timings and triggers for reappraisal and preservation actions may interact and should be aligned.

The TTRAM separates Activities and Functions into four groups: Organisational, Digital Object Management, Technology and Security.

Integrated Preservation Planning is informed by a number of Organisational Infrastructure activities and functions from the TTRAM (Figure 11).

- The Governance^{AF} function integrates:
 - External Engagement^{AF}, which includes Community Watch;

- Rights Management;
- Criteria, Assessment, Improvement, with inputs from
 - Legal & Ethical
 - Policy & Standards Management.

Together these inform Preservation and define the scope for Workflows (Digital Object Management) and Storage and Integrity (Technology).

Figure 11. TTRAM A|F that input to Integrated Preservation Planning

- In CPP terms, the appraisal/reappraisal workflows progress from Ingest through to Disposal.
- The repository specifies quality measures for digital objects and identifies their significant properties and preferred formats
- Reuse is enabled by providing digital objects in appropriate formats directly or via emulation.

Figure 12. CPPs that map unto the TTRAM Preservation AIF.

Each of the items in Figure 12 aligns with one or more EDEN Core Preservation Processes. Digital objects’ significant properties (which must be maintained), quality (e.g., fitness for reuse), and required formats (e.g., for preservation or reuse) all inform the definition of the risks to the object. Mitigation of risks can include migration of files to new formats, and/or making them available through emulation. The issue of quality will be examined in more detail by the EOSC EDEN project’s Reuse Fitness framework.

For Active Preservation repositories, these factors inform assessments that guide whether a preservation action is necessary to safeguard the digital object. However, the digital object assessment criteria (properties, formats, qualities etc.) can also be applied at multiple checkpoints in the digital object lifecycle, including by repositories that do not provide active preservation.

Figure 13. Digital Object Criteria.

An integrated preservation planning approach incorporates all of the relevant factors that influence the criteria set at each checkpoint

The criteria applied, and the checkpoints at which compliance criteria are assessed, depend on an interaction between the LoRCAP and the characteristics of the objects, depositors, users, and repository. The FIDELIS Project will explore a more granular typology of repositories based on the levels of care they offer, and variables related to objects, depositors, and users.

Acknowledgements

This paper was shared with the FIDELIS project (specifically WP5 TTRAM) and EDEN project (specifically WP1 Data and Process Framework for Digital Preservation) for comment, in line with the terms of reference for the EOSC Long Term Retention Task Force. An agreed alignment between the FIDELIS Activities and Functions and the EDEN Core Preservation Processes is in progress and this paper will be revised to align with that mapping

Appendix 1 - Glossary

Digital Object

A digital object is composed of a file or set of files (i.e. digital elements) that can be identified by a unique and persistent identifier. Any defined digital object (data and metadata) is in scope.

Repository

The term 'repository' is used in the very broad sense used by the FIDELIS project: any organisation responsible for a catalogue of digital objects.

Retention

In addition to avoiding unintended changes (through good storage and integrity practice), retention involves keeping a digital object findable and accessible for a defined period of time. During a retention period the object is kept unchanged until Reappraisal occurs or until external factors identify that a preservation action is necessary.

Active Preservation

Active preservation repositories monitor changes to technology and the needs of their designated community of users to identify whether digital objects remain findable, accessible and reusable. When an issue is detected this can act as a 'trigger' to take a preservation action e.g. conversion from an old to a new file format.

Appraisal

A digital object may either be submitted or offered to a repository. Appraisal is an optional step taking place during the Deposit & Appraisal (TTRAM) stage. It involves Deposit Compliance (LoRCAP) and can include checkpoints outlined under Digital Object Assessments and Interventions (TTRAM) and be influenced by criteria outlined under Additional Levels of Care (TTRAM). If initial Appraisal takes place within a repository, the criteria applied can be relevant for the Reappraisal process.

Reappraisal

Reappraisal is an assessment point that occurs after appraisal wherein a digital object will be assessed based on a set of reappraisal criteria. The criteria used to assess the digital object are based on, but not limited to, the digital object characteristics.

Reappraisal often occurs at the end of a period of retention and/or preservation. Based on the reappraisal assessment, retention may be continued, with or without an ongoing commitment to active preservation. Otherwise, a digital object may be disposed of and deleted, potentially after being copied to another repository for ongoing retention. Reappraisal could also be triggered early by other factors e.g. the planned closure of a repository.

Retention and Change through Curation and Preservation

A repository may undertake to retain a digital object for a set period of time, but also offer initial curation and/or active preservation. It should be clear which curation and preservation changes by the repository are permitted while maintaining the commitment to retention.

During a retention period the object is kept unchanged until Reappraisal occurs or until external factors identify that a preservation action is necessary.

Digital Object Assessments and Interventions

Before reappraisal occurs there are multiple checkpoints where digital objects may be assessed for compliance with agreed criteria. These assessments can take place during deposit and curation and may be ongoing throughout a period of preservation. Assessments may be followed by a decision (e.g. to reject at the point of deposit, or to cease retention) or an action (e.g. a curation or preservation action to ensure an object meets the required criteria). The outcomes of earlier assessments and actions will be recorded as a part of the provenance of an object and may influence later assessments up to the point of reappraisal.

Object Characteristics and External Factors

Object characteristics include file formats, metadata schemas and ontologies in addition to methods, content types and disciplinary coverage. External factors include the mission and scope of the repository (what it is charged with doing and what skills and capabilities it can provide) and permitted depositors (e.g. limited for an institutional repository).

Appendix 2 - Implied LoRCAP Metadata

This table is a selected version of the Implied Object & Repository Metadata Table¹⁴. It represents the information that should be available for a repository, derived from the object and repository metadata table.

Aspect	Implied Repository Level Information	Implied Object Level Information	Notes
Level of Care	All Levels of Care provided by the repository to objects it holds (Z, D, C, A)	Current Level of Care received by this specific object (Z, D, C, A)	Levels of care from the controlled vocabulary of levels.
Retention	Standard/Minimum/Maximum Retention Periods (Time)	Minimum Retention Period: Time Maximum Retention Period: Time Retention Start Date: YYYY-MM-DD	Essential information, independent of the level of care
	Exceptions to retention periods applied by the repository.	Exception to retention periods for this specific object.	Documented exceptions that might impact the retention period.
D. Deposit Compliance	Documented criteria that a digital object should meet at the point of deposit. Including Semantic (metadata, documentation, rights), technical (format), quality (formal data quality, scientific quality, ethical)	Link to repository level criteria in place when the object was deposited.	E.g., sufficient metadata to meet DataCite criteria when assigning a DOI. e.g., Metadata schema, version: URI e.g., Accepted formats, version: URI e.g., Quality criteria, version: URI
	Outcomes. All potential outcomes of the Deposit Compliance assessment.	Information about the outcome for this specific object.	Non-compliance causes a digital object to be rejected, or a non-compliant object may be moved forward to Initial Curation.

¹⁴ L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., & Recker, J. (2024). CoreTrustSeal Levels of Curation and Preservation: Implied Repository and Object Metadata Characteristics (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12701324>

	Exceptions. All possible exceptions to the deposit compliance criteria and outcomes.	Information about any exceptions applied to this specific object.	Documented exceptions that might override the deposit compliance criteria. E.g., an object is accepted despite low quality as it is unique or of high value.
C. Initial Curation	Documented criteria that a digital object should meet at the end of the initial curation process. Including Semantic (metadata, documentation, rights), technical (format), quality (formal data quality, scientific quality, ethical)	Link to repository level criteria in place when the object was initially curated	May include the same criteria as set for deposit compliance or go beyond these.
	Exceptions. All possible exceptions to the criteria and outcomes	Information about any exceptions applied to this specific object.	/
A. Active Preservation	Standard/Minimum/Maximum Preservation Periods (Time)	Preservation Period (Time) and Start (Date) for this specific object.	Active Preservation periods may be shorter than retention periods.
	Exceptions to Preservation periods applied by the repository.	Exception to preservation periods for this specific object.	Documented exceptions that might impact the preservation period.
	Preservation Action triggers applied by the repository	History of preservation actions applied to the specific digital object as part of provenance information.	Factors, including Semantic (metadata, documentation, rights), technical (format), quality (formal data quality, scientific quality, ethical) that might trigger a decision to take a preservation action on a digital object.

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